

Disrupting AIP-Protein Interactions for Therapeutic Advances in Infectious and Inflammatory Diseases

Version 1

Description

The aryl hydrocarbon receptor-interacting protein (AIP) is a critical regulator of cellular processes, primarily through its interactions with molecular chaperones and client proteins. AIP stabilizes the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) and influences pathways like NF- κ B, impacting immune response and inflammation. Recent findings from Marc Veldhoen's (MV) laboratory have revealed an AhR-independent role of AIP in T cell proliferation, survival, and calcium mobilization. This suggests AIP as a potential target for modulating detrimental T cell activity.

Our project aims to characterize AIP's interactions with calcineurin A isozyme c (PPP3CC/CNA3) and yeast mitochondrial escape 1-like 1 (YME1L1), and assess their druggability using computational modeling. We will utilize molecular dynamics (MD) simulations (GROMACS 2024.5 or higher, GPU version) with MM/PBSA and molecular docking calculations to identify druggable regions on AIP. A virtual screening campaign will identify small molecules capable of disrupting these interactions. Promising inhibitors will be experimentally tested at the MV lab to evaluate their potential in modulating inflammatory responses.

This project consists of three main tasks: (1) Stability Evaluation of Pre-determined Complexes: long MD simulations to evaluate AIP:PPP3CC and AIP:YME1L1 complex

stability (~4 months). (2) Identification of Key Regions on AIP and Virtual Screening: screening of ~300,000 compounds from NCI and Sigma Aldrich databases (~4 months). (3) In silico validation and scoring of promising compounds: MD simulations of the interaction between AIP and selected compounds with MM/PBSA calculations (~4 months). Tasks will be parallelized to optimize resource usage, overseen by the Principal Investigator.

Simulation data (~1000GB) will be stored transiently and transferred to AccelBio local servers for analysis. A GitHub page will host simulation data and disseminate findings to the scientific community. The project team consists of three experienced HPC users proficient in MD (GROMACS), docking (AutoDock-GPU), and MM/PBSA (g_mmpbsa), ensuring efficient execution without additional training. This study pioneers the computational exploration of AIP's immune function and represents a novel strategy for selective immunomodulatory therapies, offering an alternative to broad-spectrum immunosuppressants.

Funder

Fundação para a Ciência e a
Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grant

FCT application

Researchers

Bruno Victor (0000-0002-6472-5700), Paulo J. Costa (0000-0002-0492-6666), Pedro Suzano (0000-0002-4995-7415)

Organizations

AccelBio, FACULDADE DE CIENCIAS DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Disrupting AIP-Protein Interactions for Therapeutic Advances in Infectious and Inflammatory Diseases](#)

Description:

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Contact: [Victor Bruno \(bvictor@accelbio.pt\)](mailto:bvictor@accelbio.pt)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P.](#) | [FCT](#)

Grants: [FCT application](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Disrupting AIP-Protein Interactions for Therapeutic Advances in Infectious and Inflammatory Diseases

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Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

Since this project will be focused on running Molecular Dynamics and Molecular Docking simulations all the new data produced will be in the form of structural data and molecular dynamics trajectories (.pdb, gro, xtc). Most of the files

generated are numeric files. However, the largest individual files are binaries. All the generated file formats are in the default file format generated by GROMACS and Autodock Vina. We expect the project to generate approximately 500 Gb of data, which will be copied to our in-house servers (in zip format) to assure the backup of the information and a post-processing and analysis.

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

.pdb, .gro, .xtc, tar.gz, zip

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

100 – 1000 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

All the generated data from this project will be organized in a folder architecture fully transparent, consistent, and well-ordered manner, to allow it to be easy to find, understand and afterwards analyze. All the independent simulations will be stored in individual folders, where all the input and output files can be found. Additionally, in each one of these folders one will also find a README file, with all the explanation regarding the type of data that can be found in the folder.

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

No

3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

All the generated data in the HPC infrastructures will be copied and backup to the computational infrastructures that the research center the PI and Co-PI belong. Accelbio, BioISI research center and the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon possess all the necessary storage conditions to accommodate all the generated data in this project.

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Incremental backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Weekly

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Not applicable (no sensitive data)

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

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AccelBio

The ownership of the data and the intellectual property of the data will be managed according to the rules defined by Accelbio and University of Lisbon.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available upon completion of the project

All the data generated will be made available to other researchers at the time of completion of the project.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Accelbio

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

None of the above

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Unknown

URL

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Academic Free License 3.0

2025-04-01

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

No software will be developed in this project.

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

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ASSOCIAÇÃO ACCEL BIO

The data will be available from a repository at AccelBio, which after request, can be accessed

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

The data will be available from a repository at Accelbio, which after request, can be accessed

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